

Protoplast culture and plant regeneration from indica rice. 1. Type of callus used to initiate cell suspension. 2. Cells from the embryogenic cell suspension culture. 3. Freshly isolated protoplast. 4. Dividing protoplast. 5. Multicellular structures formed from protoplasts. 6. Globular embryoid from protoplast. 7. Organized embryogenic callus obtained from protoplast-derived colonies. 8. Albino plant from protoplast-derived callus.

a fresh medium, the protocolonies continued to grow and formed white embryogenic calli with secondary embryoids on their surfaces.

Organized sectors with cup-shaped scutellar structures (7) developed in some of the protoplast-derived calli. Six percent of the transferred calli responded, producing 11 albino plants (8). ■

Yield potential

Herbage and grain yield of deepwater rices in the field

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Some characteristics of deepwater rice—luxurious growth, poor light transmission in the canopy because of long and droopy leaves, and lodging susceptibility—can be improved by herbage removal. Deepwater rice cultivars also have traits that increase herbage production: high biomass production and very long growth duration.

Varieties may respond differently to leaf cutting. We studied the effect of leaf cutting on herbage yield, grain yield, and agronomic characteristics of deepwater rice cultivars under natural field conditions at the Huntra Rice Experiment Station in the 1989 wet season (WS). Twenty deepwater rice cultivars and two herbage treatments were evaluated. The experiment was

laid out in a split-plot design with three replications.

Dry seeds of deepwater rice cultivars were sown at 120 kg/ha onto plowed soil 5 May 1989. Seedlings emerged mid-May. The plants experienced drought

stress from mid-Jul to the first week of Aug.

Herbage was cut twice at the highest collar level of the last fully developed leaf—on 14 Aug (90 d after emergence [DE]) and 13 Sep (120 DE).

Table 1. Herbage and grain yield of 20 deepwater rice cultivars. Huntra Rice Experiment Station, Ayutthaya, Thailand, 1989 WS.^a

Cultivar	Herbage yield (t/ha)			Grain yield (t/ha)		
	90 DE	120 DE	Total	Control	Cut	Difference
Ban Daeng	0.6	0.5	1.0	2.2	2.4	+0.2
Huntra 60	0.8	0.6	1.4	3.1	3.2	+0.1
Khao Hoi	0.7	0.7	1.4	2.0	2.1	+0.0
Khao Kaset	0.6	0.7	1.3	2.2	2.5	+0.4
Khao Lod Chong	0.6	0.5	1.1	2.4	2.9	+0.5
Khao Mali	0.7	0.5	1.2	2.7	2.9	+0.1
Khao Praguad	0.8	0.6	1.4	2.4	2.8	+0.4
Khao Puang Nak	0.8	0.7	1.4	2.3	2.5	+0.2
Khao Rachinee	0.7	0.6	1.3	2.7	3.0	+0.4
Leb Mue Nahng 111	0.7	0.6	1.3	2.2	2.1	-0.1
Luang Pratharn	0.7	0.5	1.2	2.6	2.7	+0.1
Mali Tawng	0.9	0.8	1.6	2.5	2.6	+0.1
Nahng Khiew	0.6	0.6	1.2	2.5	2.5	+0.0
Pan Tawng	0.9	0.7	1.6	2.5	2.9	+0.4
Pin Gaew 56	0.6	0.5	1.1	2.0	2.4	+0.4
Plai Ngahm	0.6	0.6	1.2	2.4	2.7	+0.3
RD19	0.5	0.6	1.1	2.8	3.0	+0.2
Sai Bua	0.7	0.5	1.2	2.2	2.4	+0.1
Sam Ruang	0.6	0.5	1.1	2.6	2.6	+0.1
Tapow Gaew 161	0.7	0.6	1.4	1.8	2.0	+0.2
LSD 0.05	0.2	ns	ns			

^aDE = days after emergence.

Cultivars differed significantly in herbage yield at 90 DE, but not at the second cutting (Table 1). Mali Tawng, Pan Tawng, and Khao Puang Nak produced high herbage yields under drought stress, suggesting their potential for herbage production in deepwater areas that experience drought at the vegetative stage before flooding.

Mean grain yields were not significantly different and had no relationship to herbage yield. The relationship between grain yield differences and herbage yields was also low. The interaction between cultivars and herbage cutting was not significant, indicating a similar response to herbage cutting.

Mean grain yield of all cultivars with herbage cutting was significantly higher, a result mainly of more panicles/unit area. Spikelet number/panicle, fertility, and 1,000-grain weight were not affected by herbage cutting. Tiller number/unit area and harvest index increased significantly with herbage cutting but plant height and dry matter production at harvest decreased. Percentage of productive tillers and growth duration were not affected (Table 2).

Herbage cutting reduced plant height, but increased light transmission in the canopy, leading to higher tiller survival and, thus, to more panicles/unit area. That increased grain yield. ■

Table 2. Effect of herbage removal on agronomic characteristics of 20 deepwater rice cultivars. Huntra Rice Experiment Station, Ayutthaya, Thailand, 1989 WS.

Character	Control	Cut	Difference ^a
Grain yield (t/ha)	2.4	2.6	+ 0.20**
Panicles/m ²	103	117	+ 14**
Spikelets/panicle	120	116	- 4
Fertility (%)	87.7	86.9	- 0.88
1000-grain weight (g)	26.9	27.0	+ 0.06
Tillers/m ² at maturity	119	134	+ 15**
Productive tillers (%)	86	87	+ 1
Height (cm)	204	181	- 23**
Dry matter at harvest (t/ha)	12.3	10.3	- 2.01**
Harvest index	0.22	0.28	+ 0.06**
Duration (d)	232	232	± 0

^a** = significant at the 1% level.

Leaf venation in rice *Oryza sativa* L.

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The relationship of leaf vein frequency and components of transport system is important to better understand the assimilate and its relationship to photo-

synthesis. There is a positive correlation between the ratio of mesophyll thickness to interveinal distance in the leaf and photosynthetic rate per unit area.

We studied rice leaf vein frequency after flowering on 20 varieties during 1987-88. Veins per unit area were counted on the flag leaf of the main culm of 30 plants/variety (10/replication).

Vein frequency ranged from 5.62/mm to 3.79/mm, with an average 4.70/mm (see table). Variety 4048-3 had the

highest vein frequency. The ratio of small vein to large vein also showed considerable differences among the varieties. The highest was 5.40 for Bas 370. ■

Small and large vein frequency ratio in 20 rice varieties. Lahore, Pakistan.

Variety	Mean vein frequency	Small vein		Large vein		Small vein: large vein ratio
		Mean	CV (%)	Mean	CV (%)	
4048-3	5.62	4.29	12.90	1.33	13.57	3.22
Bas 370	5.38	4.54	1.95	0.84	10.55	5.40
1053-1-2	5.32	3.90	9.07	1.33	13.60	2.99
4439	5.32	4.07	11.53	1.25	14.40	3.26
Bas 385	5.23	3.69	5.63	1.54	10.67	2.39
PK 3729-4	4.90	4.12	8.32	0.78	11.22	5.25
IR9	4.77	3.98	8.60	0.79	9.12	5.04
IR8	4.63	3.83	4.32	0.80	4.40	4.79
PK2480-7-3-1	4.60	3.79	4.73	0.81	16.80	4.68
PK3058-2-2-2	4.59	3.81	5.86	0.78	10.65	4.88
IR28	4.58	3.80	2.37	0.78	7.59	4.87
KS282	4.56	3.77	3.19	0.79	14.86	4.71
IR6	4.56	3.77	3.57	0.78	12.43	4.78
PK2001-1-5-5-1	4.55	3.77	3.96	0.78	11.37	4.83
IR64	4.52	3.75	12.77	0.77	8.47	4.87
PK3727-5	4.50	3.84	7.29	0.77	22.20	4.99
PK1385-9-1-B-1	4.34	3.55	8.32	0.79	13.13	4.49
PK3727-2	4.32	3.55	8.33	0.77	9.25	4.61
PK1385-9-1-B-12	4.02	3.25	11.10	0.77	4.73	4.22
PK1385-9-1-B-13	3.79	2.99	2.50	0.80	14.86	3.74
LSD values	0.14	0.12	0.10	at alpha 5%		

Simulation of yield potential of rice varieties in Cauvery delta zone, Tamil Nadu

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We validated the ability of the L1D module of the MACROS simulation model developed at IRRI to predict the potential yield of rice varieties IR20, CO 43, and ADT38. The experiment was conducted in 1989 under irrigated conditions. Water, nutrients, and plant protection measures ensured that crop growth rate depended only on weather.

Experimental and simulated yields agreed more satisfactorily for local varieties CO 43 and ADT38 than for IR20 (see table). ■

Experimental and simulated grain yields of rice at TRRI, Aduthurai, India, 1989.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)		Agreement (%)
	Experimental	Simulated	
IR20	4.5	7.6	60
CO 43	5.3		6.5 81
ADT38	4.8		5.8 81